

Potentiometric Titration with Anion-exchange Resin Membrane Electrodes

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Anion-exchange resin membrane electrodes have been applied to potentiometric titrations of some halides and halates either singly or in mixture, using silver nitrate as the titrant. The membranes used have been prepared from three commercial anionites: Ionac-A-300, Amb. IR-4B, Amb. IR-400, using polystyrene binder. A standard iodide or bromide solution is placed inside the membrane electrode, which is either in the iodide or the bromide form, when outside of the electrode is in contact with a solution containing iodide or bromide either singly or in a mixture with other halides or halates. On the basis of the titration curves obtained with mixtures of halides and halates, three cases could be distinguished and have been discussed thoroughly.

The use of ion-exchange resins as membrane electrodes for the satisfactory determination of both cation and anion activities has been demonstrated by various workers. Based on the experiments of Marshall and Bergmann with clay-membrane electrodes, Wyllie and Patnode² first introduced the resin-membrane electrodes for ion-activity measurements.

The possibility of carrying out acid-base titrations with resin-membrane electrodes was first shown by Sinha³. He successfully titrated an acid with a base using cation-exchange resin membranes in their H form. The nature of the titration curve differs from that using the hydrogen or glass electrode, but like the latter a sharp break in the curve marks the end point.

Since anion-exchange resin membrane electrodes are reversible with respect to chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, iodate, and bromate^{4,5}, these may be used for similar potentiometric titrations. Lange and Schwartz⁶, MacInnes and Dole⁷, and Kolthoff and Furman⁸ have developed precision methods for the determination of some of these ions by potentiometric titration. But the procedures described by them require a great care and manipulative skill. On the other hand, the method based on measurements using resin-membrane electrodes is easy to set up and, as Sinha³ has shown in the case of chloride and sulphate ions, a fair degree of accuracy of measurement can be achieved in the precipitation titrations of these ions. In the experiments described below these titrations have been extended to the halides and to halates, either singly or in mixtures.

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1911.

2. *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 204.

3. *This Journal*, 1955, 32, 35.

4. Sinha, *ibid.*, 1954, 31, 577.

5. Basu, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 615.

6. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 129, 111.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1119.

8. "Potentiometric Titration".

EXPERIMENTAL

The membranes used for the study were prepared by the usual technique⁹ by hot moulding (120-25°) at 4000 lbs. p.s.i. an intimate mixture in suitable proportion of powdered (200 mesh) commercial anion-exchange resin (viz., IR-4B, IRA-400, Ionac-A-300 etc.) and polystyrene. The membranes thus prepared were cut into small sizes and were attached to the lower-flanged end of a pyrex tubing with "Durofix" adhesive. The membranes, thus prepared, were saturated with the desired ion by thorough and, if necessary, repeated soaking in a solution containing a high concentration of that ion. The membranes showing zero or negligible asymmetry potential were selected for the titration. The inside of the electrode vessel was filled with a potassium or sodium salt of known anion activity. The outside solution is a 10 ml anion solution of selected composition as shown in Table I, which also shows the form of the membrane used for each titration. A standard solution of 1.0*N* silver nitrate was used as the titrant for all the anions studied here. The E. M. F.s were measured against a saturated calomel electrode with ammonium nitrate—agar bridge.

The results of titrations are shown graphically in Figs. 1 to 5. The end point in the different titrations corresponds to a sudden increase of the measured E. M. F. The location of the exact equivalence point is often rather difficult. This may be represented without great error by the point of break (often quite sudden) in the direction of the curve. Following this procedure the ranges, rather than the exact values of the titre for the different titrations, have been worked out and shown in the table.

TABLE I

System.	Ion present.	Actual conc. (Molality).	Form of membrane.	Obs. molality (range).	Fig. No.
A	Iodide	0.100	Iodide	0.107—0.110	1
B	Bromide	0.100	Bromide	0.102—0.105	1
C	Iodide Iodate	0.050 0.050	Iodide	0.092—0.102	2
D	Iodide Bromate	0.050 0.050	Iodide	0.055—0.056	2
E	Iodide Chloride	0.050 0.010	Iodide	0.055—0.060	4
F	Iodide Chloride	0.050 0.050	Iodide	0.092—0.100	3
G	Iodide Bromide	0.050 0.010	Iodide	0.050—0.056	5
H	Iodide Bromide	0.050 0.050	Bromide	0.102—0.110	3
I	Bromide Chloride	0.050 0.010	Bromide	0.055—0.060	4
J	Bromide Bromate	0.050 0.050	Bromide	0.050—0.055	2
K	Bromide Chloride	0.050 0.050	Bromide	0.095—0.100	3

DISCUSSION

In the titration of mixtures of anions, a number of points have emerged which are summarised below.

The mixtures have been so chosen that the molalities of the two ions present are either equal or one is predominantly greater than the other. On the basis of the results of titrations, three different cases may be distinguished:

Case I.—When the solubility products of the silver salts (say, AgA and AgA_1) differ widely, i.e., $K_{AgA} \ll K_{AgA_1}$, and a mixture containing equal concentration of the two anions is titrated using a membrane, preferably saturated with A^- (i.e., one producing less soluble silver salt), only one break in the titration curve is obtained. The end point corresponds to the titration of A^- alone. The E. M. F. afterwards rises very steeply, but no further break for A_1^- is obtained.

FIG. 1. Br⁻ and I⁻ using Amb. IR-4B anion-exchange membrane.

FIG. 2. KI-KIO₃, KI-KBrO₃, and KBr-KBrO₃ using Amb. IR-4B membrane.

Fig. 2 represents the titration curves of the systems D and J, i.e., iodide and bromate mixture with iodide-form membrane and bromide and bromate mixture with the bromide-form membrane. In each case the break in the curve corresponds to the end point for the iodide and bromide respectively. Afterwards the curve is very steep and

shows no titration of the bromate ion. In the mixture of iodide and iodate (System C, Fig. 2), where the condition of solubility product holds good for Case I, the end point of the titration corresponds almost to the precipitation of both iodide and iodate.

FIG. 3. KBr—KCl, KI—KCl, and KBr—KI using Amb. IR—4B membrane.

the end point corresponds almost exactly to the precipitation of this one in preference to the other, even if the solubilities are not much different. Systems E, G, and I represent this case. The corresponding titration curves are shown in Figs. 4 and 5.

The main reaction during the titration is between added Ag^+ ions and halide and/or halate ions in the bulk of the solution. The other two possible secondary reactions are: (i) between Ag^+ ion and the halide ion in the resin phase or molecular adsorption of $AgNO_3$ by the resin material of the membrane; (ii) between Ag^+ ion and the halide ion which might have been exchanged for NO_3^- ion, particularly as the concentration of the latter increases as the titration proceeds.

These secondary reactions will have a much smaller free-energy change compared with the main reaction; moreover, the total amount corresponding to them will account for not more than 0.005 ml of 1N- $AgNO_3$, causing a maximum error of +0.5%.

Case III.—When the concentration of the ion forming the less soluble silver salt is considerably larger in a mixture,

The accuracy of determination of the main reaction, viz., between Ag^+ ion and the halide and/or halate ion, is determined by the solubility product of the precipitate. Thus, the accuracy of determination of the following ions, when present singly, will be more or

FIG. 4. KBr—KCl and KI—KCl with Amb. IR—4B membrane.

FIG. 5. KI—KBr with Amb. IR—4B membrane.

less in the order: iodide > bromide > chloride > iodate > bromate. In a mixture of the two, according to Kolthoff and Furman⁸, the less soluble one will precipitate so long as

$$[\text{A}^-] > [\text{A}_1^-] \cdot \frac{K_{\Delta\text{GA}}}{K_{\Delta\text{GA}_1}}$$

where A^- and A_1^- are the ions, silver salts AgA and AgA_1 of which have the solubility products, $K_{\Delta\text{GA}}$ and $K_{\Delta\text{GA}_1}$ respectively, and that the former is less than the latter. Taking the values of solubility products at 25° as $\text{AgI} = 1.5 \times 10^{-16}$; $\text{AgBr} = 7.7 \times 10^{-13}$; $\text{AgCl} = 1.6 \times 10^{-10}$; $\text{AgIO}_3 = 0.92 \times 10^{-8}$; $\text{AgBrO}_3 = 5.8 \times 10^{-5}$, the values of $K_{\Delta\text{GA}}/K_{\Delta\text{GA}_1}$ and the percentage of A^- remaining untitrated just before A_1^- begins to precipitate have been calculated and shown in Table II assuming $(\text{A}_1^-) = 0.05 \text{ N}$.

The data in the third column essentially mean the percentage concentration of the less soluble precipitate which will still be present before the second ion, concentration of which is 0.05 *N*, will begin to react. Thus in all but the chloride and bromide and bromide and iodide mixtures, the titrations are expected to be quite accurate. The more important question in the case of titrations of mixtures with the help of the membrane electrodes is whether the latter are sensitive to the second ion. If not, Ag⁺ ion added will react with the second ion, but the E.M.F. change will not be a function of its concentration and hence no end point for the second ion could be realised. If, however, the membrane is also sensitive to the second ion, the E. M. F. change will continue to be a function of the concentration of the second ion and the titration curve will show an end point corresponding to almost the sum of the two concentrations.

TABLE II

A ⁻ , A ₁ ⁻ .	K_{AgA}/K_{AgA_1} .	% of A ⁻ remaining untitrated.
I ⁻ , IO ₃ ⁻	1.63×10^{-6}	1.63×10^{-6}
I ⁻ , BrO ₃ ⁻	2.61×10^{-12}	2.61×10^{-10}
I ⁻ , Cl ⁻	9.38×10^{-7}	9.38×10^{-5}
I ⁻ , Br ⁻	1.95×10^{-4}	1.95×10^{-2}
Br ⁻ , Cl ⁻	4.81×10^{-3}	4.81×10^{-1}
Br ⁻ , BrO ₃ ⁻	1.33×10^{-8}	1.33×10^{-6}

In the case of iodide—chloride, iodide—bromide, and bromide—chloride mixtures using resin membranes in the iodide form for the first two titrations and in the bromide form for the remaining one, it is found that when the concentrations of the component ions are equal (0.05 *N* each), the total titre is almost equivalent to the sum of the amounts of the two ions present. Thus the resin, which is initially in the form of the ion first titrated, becomes gradually converted into the form of the second ion as its relative concentration increases with the progress of titration. For instance, the exchange reaction,

proceeds to the right and the resin becomes responsive to bromide ion when this ion begins to precipitate. This conversion of the resin form is possible because of the concentration effect. If, however, the concentration of the second ion is low, as in the systems E, G, and I, the conversion of the resin to the form of the second ion does not take place to the desired extent and hence the membrane is not responsive to the second ion; therefore the titration gives only the amount of the ion present in a larger proportion. Comparing systems F and H, it may be noticed that it is almost immaterial whether the resin is in the form of the ion forming the less soluble silver salt or the more soluble one.

It is further to be noted that the concentration of nitrate ions gradually increases as titration proceeds so that the form of the resin will perhaps be partly converted into the nitrate form since the mobility ratio $U_{\text{Br}}/U_{\text{NO}_3}$ is close to unity. The electrode may also be affected adversely if silver nitrate is molecularly adsorbed by the resin, or, if the colloiddally dispersed and negatively charged silver halides or halates are adsorbed on the

membrane surface. Such adsorbed materials have often been found to adhere tenaciously to the resin-membrane surface.

As a result of the several processes, which are likely to take place near about the end point of the titrations, it is quite probable that the location of the end point will be somewhat uncertain.

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